

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of secondary alcohols by tetrabutylammonium tribromide

Jaya Gosain and Pradeep K. Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, India

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Oxidation of several secondary alcohols by tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) in aqueous acetic acid leads to the formation of corresponding ketones. The reaction is first order with respect to TBATB and the alcohols. The reaction failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. There is no effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride on the reaction rate. The proposed reactive oxidizing species is tribromide ion. The oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.15$ at 298 K). The effect of solvent composition indicates that the rate increases with an increase in polarity of the solvent. The reaction is susceptible to both polar and steric effects of the substituents. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Recently, tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) has been used for the bromination of some selected organic substrates¹. However, only a few reports appear regarding their use as oxidizing and brominating agents in synthetic chemistry². There seems to be no report on the oxidation of secondary alcohols by tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB). We report here the kinetics of the oxidation of eight aliphatic secondary alcohols, 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol by TBATB in aqueous acetic acid solution.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of alcohols by TBATB results in the formation of the corresponding ketones,

The reactions are of first order with respect to TBATB. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) are independent of the initial concentration of TBATB. The rate constant increases linearly with increase in concentration of the alcohol (Table 1).

The oxidation of 2-propanol, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 1). To ascertain importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was studied. Results show the presence of a

substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2). Addition of tetrabutylammonium chloride (TBACl) had no effect on the rates of oxidation (Table 3). The rate constant of oxidation was determined in solvents containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. The rate constant was found to increase with an increase in the amount of water in the solvent mixture (Table 4). The rate constant of oxidation of ten secondary alcohols was determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated at 298 K (Table 2).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of 2-propanol by TBATB at 298 K

$10^3[\text{TBATB}]$ mol dm ⁻³	[Alcohol] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.10	3.21
1.0	0.20	6.35
1.0	0.40	12.8
1.0	0.60	19.0
1.0	0.80	25.1
1.0	1.00	31.8
1.0	1.50	47.1
2.0	0.20	6.18
4.0	0.20	6.77
6.0	0.20	6.46
8.0	0.20	6.83
1.0	0.20	6.16 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

There is no significant isokinetic relationship between activation entropy and enthalpy of the oxidation of eight secondary alcohols ($r^2 = 0.9543$). Correlation between the

calculated values of enthalpy and entropy of activation, often vitiated by the experimental errors associated with them. Exner³ suggested an alternative method of testing the validity of the isokinetic relationship. An Exner's plot at 288 and 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9985$; slope, 0.8351 ± 0.0131). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from this plot is 1147 ± 30 K. The linear isokinetic correlation suggests that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rates are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation.

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of secondary alcohols by TBATB

Alcohol	$10^4 k_2/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	288	298	308	318			
Me	14.6	31.8	66.0	140	54.6±0.6	-110±2	87.2±0.5
Et	25.2	52.8	108	210	51.4±0.2	-117±1	86.0±0.2
<i>n</i> -Pr	41.3	88.0	170	343	50.8±0.6	-114±2	84.8±0.4
<i>i</i> -Pr	70.7	142	268	505	47.2±0.3	-123±1	83.6±0.2
<i>i</i> -Bu	125	244	411	712	41.2±0.3	-138±2	82.3±0.6
<i>n</i> -Bu	51.0	99.2	192	355	46.8±0.3	-127±1	84.4±0.2
ClCH ₂	0.31	0.80	2.06	5.04	68.3±0.3	-94±2	96.3±0.5
MeOCH ₂	2.46	5.81	13.1	30.2	60.9±0.7	-103±2	91.5±0.6
Ph	112	210	415	790	47.2±0.9	-119±3	81.0±0.2
Benzhydrol	134	262	510	956	47.4±0.4	-117±1	82.0±0.3
Ben- α -D	22.3	46.1	95.0	182	50.9±0.3	-119±1	92.1±0.6
k_H/k_D	6.01	5.68	5.37	5.25			

Table 3. Effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride on the rate of oxidation of 2-propanol by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , [2-propanol] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 298 K	10^3 [TBACl] (mol dm ⁻³)						
	0.00	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)		31.8	32.3	33.5	32.8	31.0	33.1

Table 4. Effect of solvent composition in the oxidation of 2-propanol by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , [2-propanol] = 1.00 mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 298 K	% AcOH				
	25	40	50	60	72
$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	162	62.2	31.8	15.8	5.71

We carried out conductivity measurements to determine the nature of TBATB in aqueous acetic acid solution. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of TBATB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of TBATB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. The conductivity was found to increase sharply as the water content is increased initially but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. Therefore, TBATB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under our reaction conditions as

tetrabutylammonium and tribromide ions as equation (2). No effect of added tetrabutylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (2) lies far towards to the right,

Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to bromine and bromide ion and the value of the dissociation constant has been reported⁴. However, in the presence of the large excess of bromide ion, reaction (3),

will be suppressed. Thus in the present reaction the reactive oxidizing species is tribromide ion. The oxidation of alcohols by bromine is reported to be much faster⁵ as compared to this reaction. This also supports the view that bromine is not the reactive species in this oxidation.

Solvent composition effect : The increase in rate constant with an increase in polarity of the medium suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the dielectric constant is nonlinear. The solvent effect was analyzed using Grunwald-Winstein equation⁶,

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (4)$$

The plot of $\log k_2$ vs Y is linear ($r^2 = 0.9996$) with $m = 0.79 \pm 0.01$. The value of m suggests a transition state, which is more polar than the reactants. Thus considerable charge separation takes place in the transition state of the reaction.

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rate constants (k_2) of oxidation of alcohols failed to yield any significant correlation separately with Taft's⁷ σ^* and E_s . The correlation with σ^* accounts for ca. 94% of the data but correlation is not acceptable by Exner's criterion⁸.

$$\log k_2 = -1.82 (\pm 0.19) \Sigma \sigma^* - 2.25 \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9407; \text{sd} = 0.22; n = 8;$$

$$\Psi = 0.19; T = 288 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.45 (\pm 1.00) \Sigma E_2 - 2.93 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2601; \text{sd} = 0.77; n = 8; \psi = 0.75;$$

$$T = 288 \text{ K}$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ the Exner's statistical parameter⁸. The rate constants were, therefore, correlated in terms of Pavelich-Taft's⁹ dual substituent-parameter (DSP) equation,

$$\log k = \pi^* \Sigma \sigma^* + \delta \Sigma E_s + \log k_0 \quad (7)$$

The values of the substituent constants were obtained from the compilation by Wiberg⁷. The correlations are excellent; reaction constants being negative (Table 5). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2136$) between σ^* and E_s of the nine substituents.

Table 5. Temperature dependence of the reaction constants

Temp. K	ρ^*	δ	R^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.77 ± 0.01	-0.73 ± 0.02	0.9997	0.015	0.01
298	-1.68 ± 0.01	-0.72 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.006	0.01
308	-1.59 ± 0.02	-0.64 ± 0.01	0.9989	0.005	0.03
318	-1.50 ± 0.01	-0.56 ± 0.02	0.9998	0.011	0.01

The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant, points to a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of the high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product, acetone as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energy of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results. The faster oxidation of 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol may well be due to the stabilization of the electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state by phenyl groups through resonance.

Mechanism :

There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate complex in the present reaction. However, its formation in small amounts cannot be ruled out. In the oxidation of primary aliphatic alcohols by TBATB¹⁰, we observed Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to reductant, which suggests the formation of an intermediate complex in a pre-equilibrium. It is possible that in the present reaction also an intermediate complex is formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium but the equilibrium constant is very small. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.68$ at 298 K) confirms that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. In view of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this reaction. However, with the present data, it is not possible to state definitely about the nature of the complex. Heasley *et al.*¹¹ proposed that a complex might be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pairs of electrons of the alcohol-oxygen and tribromide ion. The formation of similar complexes has also been postulated in the oxidation of aldehydes¹² and diols¹³ with hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) as well as in the oxidation of alcohols¹⁴ and organic acids¹⁵ by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB). The formation of moderately stable complexes is supported by the values of thermodynamic parameters also. The complex formation is favored by the enthalpy term but there is a loss of entropy, indicating the formation of a rigid structure.

The large negative reaction constant and a substantial deuterium kinetic isotope effect suggest a considerable carbocation character in the transition state. Therefore, the mechanism (Scheme 1) involving transfer of a hydride ion from the alcohol to the oxidant, in the rate-determining step, is suggested.

The observed negative entropy of activation also supports it. As the charge separation takes place, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy¹⁶.

Experimental

All the alcohols were commercial products (Fluka) and dried over magnesium sulfate and then fractionated. Benzhydrol was recrystallized from ethanol. TBATB was prepared by reported method¹⁷ and its purity checked by iodometric method. Benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was prepared by reported method¹⁸. The isotopic purity of PhCDOHPh, as ascertained by its NMR spectra, was $93 \pm 5\%$. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionally distilled. All other reagents were commercial products and were purified by the usual methods¹⁹.

The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions, i.e. with an excess of alcohol over TBATB. In a typical experiment, a mixture of 2-propanol (0.05 mol), KBr (0.2 mol) and TBATB (0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml with 1 : 1 (v/v) aqueous acetic acid and kept in the dark for ≈ 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.21 g (93%) and 1.97 g (81%), respectively, based on the consumption of TBATB. The DNP was found to be identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with the DNP of acetone. In similar experiments, with other alcohols, the yields of the DNP were in the range 78–89% after recrystallization.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess

($\times 15$ or greater) of the substrate over TBATB. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, unless mentioned otherwise. Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to a large extent to bromine and bromide ion. The value⁴ of the dissociation constant 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water was found to be $\sim 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. To suppress the dissociation, all kinetic runs were carried out in the presence of an excess (0.2 mol dm^{-3}) of potassium bromide. The reactions were studied at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$) and were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of TBATB at 394 nm for up to 80% reaction. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from linear plots ($r > 0.995$) of $\log [\text{TBATB}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. Simple and multivariate regression analyses were carried out by the least-squares method. The second order rate constant (k_2) was determined from the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$.

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